

Studies in Copper (II) Chelates: Part IV. On the Tetragonality of Bis(1-Amidino-O-Alkylurea) Copper(II) and mixed Chelate Formation with α , α' -Dipyridyl and o-Phenanthroline

R. L. Dutta* and Dhruvananda De

The solution absorption spectra of a series of bis(1-amidino-O-alkylurea) (alkyl=methyl, ethyl, iso-propyl and n-butyl) copper (II) complexes in different solvents indicate the following decreasing order of tetragonality :

Extensive spectral measurements and molar ratio variation indicate a 1:1 complex formation between the complex and α , α' -dipyridyl or o-phenanthroline. This has been shown to be producing in solution a mixed chelate of the type $[\text{Cu}(\text{dipy})(\text{AAUH})]^{2+}$ aq. or $[\text{Cu}(\text{o-phen})(\text{AAUH})]^{2+}$ aq. having a distorted octahedral structure. Formation constants of the mixed complexes have also been evaluated and these are of the order of 10^7 — 10^8 .

A few earlier papers¹ in the series described our studies on the mixed chelate formation of the type $[(\text{Cu}(\text{dipy})(\text{BigH}))^{2+}]$ and $[(\text{Cu}(\text{o-phen})(\text{BigH}))^{2+}]$. These studies logically suggested attempts to synthesize similar mixed chelates of copper (II) with the 1-amidino-O-alkylurea and α , α' -dipyridyl or o-phenanthroline. In a series of publications²⁻⁷ from this Laboratory, it has been suggested that the 1-amidino-O-alkylurea ligands are comparable to biguanides, although the copper (II) and Nickel (II) complexes are some slightly weaker than their biguanide analogues.

Attempts to isolate the desired mixed chelates in solid, crystalline state did not quite materialise and therefore, we have undertaken extensive measurements in solution. These studies along with some studies on the extent of tetragonality of the complexes form the subject matter of this paper.

The bis(1-amidino-O-alkylurea) copper (II) acetates are all rose-red in the solid crystalline state and their reasonable solubility in several solvents such as water, ethanol, ethyleneglycol and dimethylsulfoxide provided a scope to throw some light on the tetragonality of the complexes. Being under the influence of possible tetragonal and Jahn-Teller distortion⁸ the copper(II) complexes, which are predominantly square-planar, may add on solvent molecules along the d_{z^2} orbital. In the event of extreme tetragonality,

*Present Address : Department of Chemistry, Ohio State University, Columbus, Ohio, U. S. A.

1. R. L. Dutta, D. De and A. Syamal (in part), *This Journal*, 1968, **45**, 663.

2. R. L. Dutta and P. Rây, *This Journal*, 1959, **36**, 567, 576.

3. R. L. Dutta, *This Journal*, 1960, **37**, 499.

4. R. L. Dutta, B. Sur and N. R. Sengupta, *This Journal*, 1960, **37**, 565, 573.

5. R. L. Dutta and S. Lahiry, *This Journal*, 1960, **37**, 789; 1961, **38**, 689.

6. R. L. Dutta and A. Syamal, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1965, **27**, 2447.

7. R. L. Dutta and A. Syamal, *Coord. Chem. Revs.*, 1967, **2**(4), 441; *This Journal*, 1968, **45**, (3), 115, 219, 226.

8. C. J. Ballhausen, "Introduction to Ligand Field Theory", McGraw Hill, New York, 1962, p. 268.

the octahedral or distorted octahedral complexes will pass on to square-planar complexes.⁹ A large number of the bis(1-amidino-O-alkylurea) (alkyl=methyl, ethyl, isopropyl and n-butyl) copper(II) complexes were dissolved in the above mentioned solvents and their absorption spectra run closely. These studies visually showed that the dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO) solutions were bright rose-red (free from any violet or bluish tinge) and these in water were red-violet (with a bluish tinge). In keeping with these visual observations, the λ_{\max} (for the methyl derivative, say,) varied from 490-500 μ (20,410—20,000 cm^{-1}) in DMSO to 545—555 μ (18,350—18,020 cm^{-1}) in water. The ethanol or the ethyleneglycol spectra provided intermediate values of λ_{\max} . These results point directly to the weak donor ability of DMSO compared to ethanol and water and these observations are in keeping with the respective positions of these solvent-ligands in the spectrochemical series¹⁰. Therefore in DMSO, the copper(II) complexes have extreme tetragonality, leading to a square-planar structure, which is accentuated by the absorption band appearing around 490—500 μ (20,410—20,000 cm^{-1}), being typical of square-planar copper(II) complex with four nitrogen coordination. The details of the band positions appear in Table I. A comparable case exists in the study of the tetragonality of bis (ethylenediamine) copper (II) complex.⁹

TABLE I

Tetragonality of [Cu(AAUH)₂](Ac)₂ in different solvents.

Complex	Solvent	Absorption spectral Band (cm^{-1})	ϵ_{\max}
[Cu (AMUH) ₂](Ac) ₂	DMSO	20,410—20,000	37.40
	EtOH	19,160—19,050	*
	Etglycol	18,520—18,180	41.25
	H ₂ O	18,350—18,020	36.50
[Cu (AEUH) ₂](Ac) ₂	DMSO	20,200—19,800	41.25
	EtOH	19,050—18,690	36.40
	Etglycol	18,520—18,180	37.21
	H ₂ O	18,350—18,020	39.25
[Cu (APr ⁿ UH) ₂](Ac) ₂	DMSO	20,410—20,000	43.00
	EtOH	19,230—18,870	42.50
	Etglycol	18,690—18,350	40.00
	H ₂ O	18,350—18,020	43.00
[Cu (ABu ⁿ UH) ₂](Ac) ₂	DMSO	20,410—20,000	43.00
	EtOH	19,230—18,870	43.00
	Etglycol	18,690—18,350	41.25
	H ₂ O	18,350—18,020	42.00

DMSO=Dimethylsulfoxide; Etglycol=Ethyleneglycol; AAUH=1-amidino-O-alkylurea; AMUH=1-amidino-O-methylurea; AEUH=1-amidino-O-ethylurea; APrⁿUH=1-amidino-O-isopropylurea; ABuⁿUH=1-amidino-O-n-butylurea.

*The optical density was measured in saturated solution. Due to some uncertainty in the total solubility of the complex, extinction co-efficient is rather of poor accuracy and hence not mentioned in the Table I.

Next we studied the solution absorption spectra of all the above five complexes in the presence of added α - α' -dipyridyl or o-phenanthroline. In all cases, the red-violet

colour in aqueous solution of the pure bis(1-amidino-O-alkylurea) copper(II) changed to deep blue-violet, the λ_{\max} . changing from around 550 $m\mu$ to about 570—590 $m\mu$ (at pH 9.0) and to 630—680 $m\mu$ around the optimum pH of formation. Molar ratio variation between the complex and the heterocyclic ligands at more than one wavelength confirms the formation of a 1 : 1 chelate standing for any of the following three reactions :

- (1) $[Cu(AAUH)_2] (Ac)_2 + \text{dipy} \longrightarrow [Cu (\text{dipy}) (H_2O)_2](Ac)_2 + 2 AAUH$;
- (2) $[Cu(AAUH)_2] (Ac)_2 + \text{dipy} \longrightarrow [Cu(AAUH)_2 (\text{dipy})] (Ac)_2$;
- (3) $[Cu(AAUH)_2] (Ac)_2 + \text{dipy} \longrightarrow [Cu(AAUH) (\text{dipy})] (Ac)_2 + AAUH$.

(AAUH = 1-amidino-O-alkylurea).

The complex $[Cu(\text{dipy}) (H_2O)_2] (Ac)_2$ might also stay at the pH of these studies (pH 7.0)

as a di- μ -hydroxo bridged complex $[(\text{dipy}) Cu \begin{array}{c} \swarrow \text{OH} \\ \searrow \text{OH} \end{array} Cu(\text{dipy})] (Ac)_2$. That the system

did not result in the formation of a mere dipyriddy complex, was verified, by running the spectra of one mole copper(II) acetate and one mole dipyriddy under the same condition. This latter interaction provided a blue solution only, whose solution spectra was radically different from the spectra of the mixed chelate system. We proved that the reaction occurred as (3) releasing AAUH to the same extent as the starting mole of the complex $[Cu(AAUH)_2] (Ac)_2$. We ran a spectra having 0.008 mole $[Cu(AAUH)_2] (Ac)_2$, 0.008 mole α, α' -dipyriddy shaken and after the formation of the mixed chelate was complete, added 0.004 mole $Cu(Ac)_2$ so as to bind the released 0.008 mole AAUH as 0.004 mole $[Cu(AAUH)_2] (Ac)_2$ (at pH 7.0). It was found out that the experimentally observed spectra in presence of added copper (II) acetate was fairly close to the mixed spectra of 0.008 M $[Cu(AAUH)_2] (Ac)_2$, 0.008 M dipyriddy and add 0.004 M $[Cu(AAUH)_2] (Ac)_2$. These studies revealed with a fair amount of certainty the formation in solution of the mixed chelate $[Cu(\text{dipy}) (AAUH)] (Ac)_2$, with possibly, aqua molecule also participating in the coordination sphere. Exactly similar results were obtained for the o-phenanthroline system.

The summarised band positions of all these systems appear in Table II. The considerable shifting of the original band of $[Cu(AMUH)_2] (Ac)_2$ from 20,000 cm^{-1} (DMSO) to 14,700—to 15,600 cm^{-1} in aqueous medium in the presence of the heterocyclic ligands points to the square-planar structure being strained to a distorted octahedral

TABLE II

Electronic spectra of the mixed chelates in Aqueous medium

System	Optimum pH of formation	Absorption Spectral Band (cm^{-1})	ϵ_{\max}
1. $[Cu (AMUH)_2] (Ac)_2$ and dipyriddy	6.0—6.5	15,620—14,710	63.15
2. $[Cu(AMUH)_2] (Ac)_2$ and o-phenanthroline.	5.5—6.0	15,380—14,710	54.37
3. $[Cu(AEUH)_2] (Ac)_2$ and dipyriddy	7.0	15,870—14,930	64.50
4. $[Cu (AEUH)_2] (Ac)_2$ and o-phenanthroline	5.5—6.0	15,380—14,710	53.75
5. $[Cu(\text{BigH})_2] Cl_2$ and dipyriddy	5.5—7.0	16,950—15,880	63.75
6. $[Cu(\text{BigH})_2] Cl_2$ and o-phenanthroline	6.0—7.0	16,950—15,880	56.25

structure. A comparison with the spectra of the mixed chelates $[\text{Cu}(\text{dipy}) (\text{BigH})] \text{X}_2$ and $[\text{Cu}(\text{o-phen}) (\text{BigH})] \text{X}_2$ in aqueous solution indicates somewhat greater distortion in the structures of the 1-amidino-O-alkylurea mixed chelates.

Formation constants of the mixed chelate systems were evaluated by following the same procedure as for the corresponding biguanide—dipyridyl mixed chelates¹. The optical density values were analysed in order to evaluate the concentration of the mixed chelate and the $[\text{Cu}(\text{dipy})]^{2+}$ or $[\text{Cu}(\text{o-phen})]^{2+}$ and the concn. of the free (AAUH) was obtained from a knowledge of the pH of the system and the dissociation constant of the ligands concerned. Details are given in the Table III. The values compare favourably with the corresponding biguanide chelates. During all the solution studies no attempt was made to maintain ionic strength constant by the addition of an electrolyte such as KCl, or KNO_3 etc. because of solubility limitations.

TABLE III

*Formation constants of the Mixed chelates*Initial concn. of $[\text{Cu} (\text{AAUH})_2] (\text{Ac})_2 = 0.008 \text{ M}$ Initial concn. of α, α' -dipyridyl or o-phenanthroline = 0.008 MWavelength of measurements = 660 m μ

$\epsilon[\text{Cu}(\text{dipy})(\text{AMUH})] (\text{Ac})_2$	=	63.15	$\epsilon[\text{Cu} (\text{o-phen}) (\text{AMUH})] (\text{Ac})_2$	=	54.37
$\epsilon[\text{Cu} (\text{dipy}) (\text{AEUH})] (\text{Ac})_2$	=	64.50	$\epsilon[\text{Cu} (\text{o-phen}) (\text{AEUH})] (\text{Ac})_2$	=	53.75
$\epsilon[\text{Cu} (\text{dipy})]^{2+}$	=	46.87	$\epsilon[\text{Cu} (\text{o-phen})]^{2+}$	=	45.00

System	pH of measurement	O.D. 1 cm cell	Concn. of $[\text{Cu} (\text{dipy})]^{2+}$ or $[\text{Cu} (\text{o-phen})]^{2+}$	[Mixed complex]	[AMUH] of [AEUH]	K
1. $[\text{Cu} (\text{AMUH})_2] (\text{Ac})_2$ and α, α' -dipyridyl	5.0	0.454	0.003132 M	0.004868 M	$4.397 \times 10^{-8} \text{ M}$	3.53×10^7
2. $[\text{Cu} (\text{AMUH})_2] (\text{Ac})_2$ and o-phenanthroline	5.5	0.478	0.001659	0.006341	1.213×10^{-7}	3.15×10^7
	5.0	0.410	0.002668	0.005332	4.211×10^{-8}	4.74×10^7
3. $[\text{Cu} (\text{AEUH})_2] (\text{Ac})_2$ and α, α' -dipyridyl	4.5	0.428	0.004991	0.003009	3.091×10^{-9}	1.95×10^8
	5.0	0.456	0.003403	0.004597	8.865×10^{-9}	1.52×10^8
4. $[\text{Cu} (\text{AEUH})_2] (\text{Ac})_2$ and o-phenanthroline	4.5	0.394	0.004114	0.003886	2.880×10^{-9}	3.27×10^8
	5.0	0.410	0.002286	0.005714	7.995×10^{-9}	3.12×10^8
5. $[\text{Cu} (\text{BigH})_2] \text{Cl}_2$ and α, α' -dipyridyl	4.5					1.69×10^9
	5.0					1.85×10^9
6. $[\text{Cu} (\text{BigH})_2] \text{Cl}_2$ and o-phenanthroline	4.5					2.27×10^9
	5.0					1.88×10^9

EXPERIMENTAL

Bis(1-amidino-O-alkylurea) (alkyl=methyl, ethyl, isopropyl, n-butyl) copper(II) acetates were prepared by following published procedures¹¹. Copper content was estimated iodometrically and water content was determined by heating at 110-115° for one hour.

10. R. S. Drago, "Physical Methods in Inorganic Chemistry", Reinhold Publishing Corporation, New York, 1965.

11. R. L. Dutta and P. Rây, *This Journal*, 1959, **36**, 567.

Complex	% Cu	% H ₂ O
1. [Cu(AMUH) ₂] (Ac) ₂ · 4H ₂ O	Found : 13.31 Calcd. : 13.39	14.70 14.81
2. [Cu (AEUH) ₂] (Ac) ₂ · 4.5H ₂ O	Found : 12.11 Calcd. : 12.15	15.39 15.48
3. [Cu (APr ⁱ UH) ₂] (Ac) ₂ · 2H ₂ O	Found : 12.63 Calcd. : 12.56	7.20 7.12
4. [Cu (ABu ⁿ UH) ₂] (Ac) ₂ · 1.5H ₂ O	Found : 12.16 Calcd. : 12.11	5.15 5.14

Copper(II) acetate dihydrate was B.D.H.L.R. sample. α , α' -dipyridyl and o-phenanthroline were B.D.H.A.R. Grade.

Absorption spectral measurements were made by Hilger and Watts UVISPEK spectrophotometer using 1 cm. effective light path over the range of 400—750 m μ .

Solution spectral studies on the composition and formation pH range were run at 0.008 M bis (1-amidino-O-alkylurea) copper (II) acetate level. The weighed complex was dissolved in about 15 ml water, then weighed amount of α , α' -dipyridyl or o-phenanthroline dissolved in little spirit was added, pH adjusted to the desired value using a Beckman Zeromatic pH meter and finally volume made upto 25ml with water. pH variations were made with 0.008M copper(II) bis (1-amidino-O-alkylurea) acetate, 0.008 M α , α' -dipyridyl/o-phenanthroline in the range pH 4.5—pH 9.0 (cf Fig. 1). Molar ratio

FIG. 1

Effect of pH on the absorption spectra of different complexes.

- (1) [Cu (AEUH)₂] (Ac)₂ 4.5H₂O, 0.008 M and α , α' -dipyridyl, 0.008M at pH 4.5
- (2) [Cu (AEUH)₂] (Ac)₂ 4.5 H₂O, 0.008M and α , α' -dipyridyl, 0.008M at pH 5.5
- (3) [Cu (AEUH)₂] (Ac)₂ 4.5 H₂O, 0.008M and α , α' -dipyridyl, 0.008M at pH 7.
- (4) [Cu (AEUH)₂] (Ac)₂ 4.5 H₂O, 0.008M at pH 7.0
- (5) [Cu (AEUH)₂] (Ac)₂ 4.5H₂O, 0.008M and α , α' -dipyridyl, 0.008M at pH 8.
- (6) [Cu (AEUH)₂] (Ac)₂ 4.5 H₂O, 0.008M and α , α' -dipyridyl, 0.008M at pH 9.

variations were done at constant (0.008 M) copper(II) bis(1-amidino-O-alkylurea) acetate, varying α , α' -dipyridyl/o-phenanthroline (0.002 M—0.014 M) at a fixed optimum pH of formation of the mixed complex.

We are grateful to the U.G.C., New Delhi, for providing a research scholarship to one of us (D.D.).